

Technical Methodological Annex: Search Strategy and Boolean Strings for the Systematic Review on Agroforestry Models (1980-2025)

This technical document provides specific details regarding the strategy and boolean strings used in the bibliographic searches conducted for the systematic review on agroforestry modeling, following the methodological guidelines of PRISMA 2020. The objective is to facilitate reproducibility, transparency, and methodological auditing by other researchers.

Boolean Strings Used

Scopus (953 documents retrieved) TITLE (agricultur* OR forest* OR agroforest*) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ("partial equilibrium" OR "computable general equilibrium" OR CGE OR "linear programming" OR "mathematical programming" OR "sector model" OR "policy model" OR FASOM OR GTM OR EFISCEN OR MOSAICC OR G4M OR GAMS) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ("climate change" OR sustainab* OR GHG OR mitigation OR adaptation OR resilience OR "supply chain" OR trade) AND PUBYEAR > 1969 AND PUBYEAR < 2026 AND (SUBJAREA (AGRI) OR SUBJAREA (ENVI) OR SUBJAREA (ECON))

Web of Science Core Collection (412 documents retrieved) TI=(agricultur* OR forest* OR agroforest*) AND TS=("partial equilibrium" OR "computable general equilibrium" OR CGE OR "linear programming" OR "mathematical programming" OR "sector model" OR "policy model" OR FASOM OR GTM OR EFISCEN OR MOSAICC OR G4M OR GAMS) AND TS=("climate change" OR sustainab* OR "greenhouse gas" OR GHG OR mitigation OR adaptation OR resilience OR "supply chain" OR trade) AND PY=1970-2025 AND WC=(AGRICULTURE, MULTIDISCIPLINARY OR FORESTRY OR ECONOMICS)

IEEE Xplore (225 documents retrieved) ("agriculture" OR "forest" OR "agroforest") AND ("partial equilibrium" OR "computable general equilibrium" OR "optimization" OR "linear programming" OR "mathematical programming" OR "mathematical model" OR "decision support" OR "resource allocation") AND ("climate change" OR sustainability OR mitigation OR adaptation OR GHG)
Content Type: Journals, Magazines, Books Years: 1980-2025

EconPapers (69 documents retrieved) ("agriculture sector model" OR FASOM OR GTM OR EFISCEN) AND (agriculture OR forest) AND ("climate change" OR sustainability OR "SDG 2" OR "SDG 12" OR "SDG 13" OR "SDG 15" OR "sustainable development goal" OR "food security" OR "biodiversity" OR "resource efficiency" OR "land use")

This document aims to facilitate the reproducibility of the study through clear documentation of the strategies employed during the search process.

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